

Supporting Information for "Asymmetric Backward Peaking Radiation Pattern from a Relativistic Particle Accelerated by Lightning Leader Tip Electric Field"

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Introduction Supporting information figure (S1) is created to explain the novel Bremsstrahlung asymmetry control parameter R , and how it is related to a particle's trajectory by referring to the real-life example of a car's trajectory. Curved car trajectory, orientates car such that electromagnetic radiation emitted by the headlights of the car leaves asymmetric radiation pattern reflections on the road. In addition, asymmetric radiation patterns on the road are independent of the observer's position. Hence, it is asymmetric regardless of an observation point.

Figure S1.

Particle and Car Rotating in The Opposite Directions – Particle in Anti-Clockwise and Car in Clockwise Direction.

Asymmetric Radiation Beam Emitted by Anti-Clockwise Rotating (Bremsstrahlung Only) Charged Particle Can Be Resembled in this case To a Asymmetric Headlight Radiation of The Clockwise Rotating Car.

Same radiation asymmetry at the back of the car and particle rotating in the same anti-clockwise direction.